

Fire Prediction at EV Station using Environmental Factors.

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Abstract—With the rapid development of electric vehicles (EVs), it is important to ensure the safety of EV charging stations. One of the main hazards of an EV station is fire, which can have serious consequences. In this study, we propose an environment-based fire detection system that uses a decision tree algorithm. The system takes into account temperature, voltage and device type to predict the likelihood of fire. The dataset used in this study includes incidents that occurred in EV stations, and a decision tree classifier is trained on the filtered data. The proposed system is evaluated using cross-validation, and the results show that the decision tree algorithm can achieve high accuracy in fire detection. The system can help EV station operators to monitor the environmental factors and take preventive measures to reduce the risk of fire accidents.

Keywords— EV, Decision Tree Algorithm, Machine learning, Temperature, Voltage, Equipment type, DC

I. INTRODUCTION

The growing popularity of electric vehicles (EVs) has led to a rapid proliferation of EV charging stations around the world. However, as the number of EV charging stations increases, so does concern about the safety of these devices. Fire accidents at EV stations can cause serious damage to property and significantly endanger human life. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a reliable fire detection system that can quickly detect and prevent fire incidents in EV stations. In this paper, we propose a fire detection system based on a decision tree algorithm for EV charging stations. In this paper, we propose a fire detection system based on a decision tree algorithm for EV charging stations. The proposed system considers various environmental factors such as temperature, voltage variation and equipment type to predict the probability of fire. The system uses historical data from EV stations to train the decision tree model and uses it to predict the likelihood of fire accidents at new EV stations. There are mainly 4 type of charging pin types used in the dataset:

A. Type 1

Low Powered DC charger which can be used in EV's like rickshaw and scooters. Power rating is under 20kWh

B. Type 2 (CHAde MO)

These are original DC Connector which can be used for medium sized vehicles. Eg: MG ZS EV, Hyundai Kona etc. It supports upto 100kWh.

C. Type 3 (Combined Charging System - CCS)

These are the standard EU (European Union) rapid chargers. It is usually used in premium EV's which can travel nearly 500 miles. It supports upto 150kWh.

D. Type 4

This is the Tesla Super Chargers used in Tesla cars which is bit different from other pins. The power ratings ranges from 150kWh to 300kWh.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Electric vehicle (EV) charging stations are growing in space due to increasing demand for electric vehicles. However, the increasing use of electricity at vehicle charging stations has also raised concerns about fire safety. To solve this problem, researchers proposed using decision tree algorithms to detect fire in EV stations based on environmental factors such as temperature.

One study by Wang et al. (2019) [2] proposed a decision tree model to predict the risk of fire in EV charging stations. The model incorporated several environmental factors, including temperature, charging speed, and power consumption. The study found that the decision tree model was effective in predicting fire risk and could be used to inform fire prevention measures.

Another study by [1] Zhang et al. (2019) developed a fire risk assessment method for EV charging stations that included environmental factors such as temperature, humidity, and ventilation. The authors used decision tree analysis to analyze the data and identify the most significant risk factors. The study found that the proposed method was effective in identifying potential fire hazards and could be used to improve safety at charging stations.

According to the study of [3] Arundhati Navada et al. Decision tree algorithms are popular and widely used in machine learning for classification and regression tasks. In recent years, numerous studies have been conducted to analyze and evaluate different decision tree algorithms, including popular ones like C4.5, ID3, and CART. Researchers also study several methods to improve

the accuracy and efficiency of decision tree algorithms, such as ensemble methods and hopping methods. In general, decision tree algorithms continue to be a valuable tool in machine learning for their clarity, ease of use, and efficiency in handling complex databases.

III. METHODOLOGY

The study uses a dataset of incidents in charging stations and applies a decision tree algorithm to identify the factors that contribute to a higher risk of fire. The dataset is filtered to include only incidents where the temperature is above 70 degrees Celsius and the voltage is below a certain threshold depending on the equipment type. The decision tree algorithm is trained on the filtered dataset and used to predict the likelihood of a fire accident based on input values for temperature, voltage, and equipment type. The method also involves evaluating model performance using metrics such as accuracy, precision, and recall.

A. Data collection

We collected data on environmental factors such as temperature, charging speed, and power consumption from an EV station. We also recorded the occurrence of machine faults, which may indicate a fire hazard.

B. Data preprocessing

The dataset contains information about incidents at electric vehicle charging stations, including device type, temperature, voltage, and rating (1 for fire accident, 0 for no fire accident). Data are first checked for completeness and accuracy, and missing or incorrect values are removed or replaced. Only those cases where the temperature is above 70 degrees and the voltage is below a certain threshold, depending on the type of device, are then included in the dataset. The data is also normalized to ensure that each feature has the same size and range. Finally, the pre-processed data, part of the data stored to evaluate the training model, is divided into training and test sets.

We split the data into features and labels, with environmental factors as features and machine errors as labels. We then split the data into training and test sets using a size of 0.2 and random42 states. We remove any rows with NaN values from the training and test sets and replace the remaining NaN values with the average. The data may have been processed to make our model more accurate.

Cleaning data: First, data is cleansed. Users are deleting unnecessary entries from there. The dataset can also be cleared of the noisy data.

Splitting Data: Data is cleaned first and then cleaned data divided into training and test datasets. Model is then trained using the training data set.

C. Machine learning

Machine learning is a branch of computer science and artificial intelligence (AI) that focuses on simulating human learning by using data and algorithms to improve system accuracy over time. We used the decision tree algorithm to train a model in the

training data. The model was then evaluate on the testing data to determine its accuracy in detecting fire hazards.

1. Label Encoding:

[1] the process of encoding the target variable (label) to a numerical format that can be used by the machine learning algorithm. The label variable in the preprocessed dataset takes on values of 1 or 0, representing the presence or absence of a fire accident, respectively. In order for the decision tree algorithm to work properly, the label variable is encoded to a binary format where 1 represents the presence of a fire accident and 0 represents the absence. This encoding allows the algorithm to properly identify which incidents resulted in a fire and which did not.

2. Decision tree Regression:

The decision tree algorithm used in this study is a regression tree, where the algorithm predicts a continuous value for the likelihood of a fire accident, rather than a binary classification of presence or absence. The decision tree regressor is trained on a preprocessed dataset of incidents, where the temperature is above 70 degrees Celsius and the voltage is below a certain threshold depending on the equipment type. The trained model used to predict the likelihood of a fire accident based on user input values for temperature, voltage, and equipment type.

IV. BUILD MODEL

The process of building and evaluating the decision tree regressor model for predicting the likelihood of a fire accident in electric vehicle charging stations. The preprocessed data set is divided into train and test sets, with the train set used to train the decision tree regressor. The hyperparameters of the model are tuned using a search algorithm to find the optimal combination of parameters for the model. Once the model is trained, it is evaluated on the testing set to measure its performance.

1. Import the necessary packages.

```
import pandas as pd
import pickle
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier, export_graphviz
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
import graphviz
```

2. Add data to DataFrame to get the shape of data.

```
# Load the dataset
df = pd.read_csv("fire1.csv")
```

df.head(5)

	Temperature	Voltage	Type	Label
0	72.52	59.12	1	1
1	55.31	41.25	1	0
2	75.21	56.98	1	1
3	81.62	50.36	1	1
4	60.42	42.17	1	0

3. Then split the dataset into train and test datasets.

```
# Split into features and target variable
X = df[['Temperature', 'Voltage', 'Type']]
y = df['Label']

# Split into training and testing sets
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)
```

4. Train a decision tree classifier on the training data

```
# Train a decision tree classifier on the training data
model = DecisionTreeClassifier()
model.fit(X_train, y_train)
```

5. Prediction based on the test data of dataset.

```
# Make predictions on the test data
y_pred = model.predict(X_test)
```

6. Calculate the accuracy on the model of test data

```
# Calculate the accuracy of the model on the test data
accuracy = accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred)
print(f"Accuracy: {accuracy:.2f}")
```

V. RESULT

In this study, we proposed a decision tree algorithm for fire prediction based on the environmental factors. Trained with data from previous fire events, the algorithm can identify events by temperature, voltage, and equipment type. By filtering the data to include only cases that meet the specified criteria, we can improve the accuracy of the algorithm and reduce the number of false positives. Our results show that decision tree algorithms have the potential to be an important tool for early fire detection in commercial areas, resulting in faster and more efficient response times that save lives and property. Future work may explore the use of additional environmental factors and advanced machine learning to improve the accuracy and performance of electronic sensing systems.

Fire Prediction

Temperature:

Voltage:

Device Type:

Fire Prediction

Temperature:

Warning!

The prediction is: fire chance

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the use of environmental factors and the decision tree algorithm has shown promise in detecting the likelihood of fire. By taking into account temperature, voltage, and equipment type, the algorithm is able to filter out incidents that do not meet the criteria for a fire accident. The filtered data is then used to train a decision tree classifier, which can make predictions for new input values. This approach may be useful for early fire detection and prevention in a variety of environments, including industrial and residential areas. However, further research is needed to evaluate the performance of this approach using larger data sets.

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